

A Reinvestigation of Bicarbonate Induced Oligomerization of Ethyl Acetoacetate : One-pot Biomimetic Synthesis of Dimethylcoumarin, Trimethylcoumarin and Condensed Coumarin Derivatives^{†#}

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In addition to the previously reported products dehydroacetic acid (1) and a pyranopyran derivative, presently revised as 4,7-dimethyl-2H-pyrano-[3,2-c]-2H-pyran-2,5-dione (2), seven new polysubstituted coumarin derivatives have been synthesised by NaHCO₃ catalyzed self-condensation of ethyl acetoacetate. The new products have been characterized as 3-acetyl-6-carboethoxy-5-hydroxy-4,7-dimethylcoumarin (3), 5-hydroxy-4,7-dimethylcoumarin (4), 3-acetyl-6-carboethoxy-4,5,7-trimethylcoumarin (5), 6-carboethoxy-4,5,7-trimethylcoumarin (6), 9-carboethoxy-10-hydroxy-2,4,8-trimethylbenzo-[3,4]-coumarin (7) and 8-carboethoxy-3,7,9-trimethylfuran-[3,2-c]-coumarin (8) based on their ¹H and ¹³C nmr, and mass spectral studies in conjunction with the mechanistic rationale of their formation and some chemical evidence. In the same way the remaining new product is tentatively assigned 3''-carboethoxy-7,9,10,10'-tetramethyl-tetrahydrofuran-[2,4-de]-4',10'-dihydro-[5,6]-naphthopyran-2,5-dione (9) structure. Transformations of 3 to 4, 5 to 6 (minor), 6-carboethoxy-4,5,7-trimethylcoumarin (10) and 4,5,7-trimethylcoumarin (11), and 6 to 11 have been effected by heating with conc. H₂SO₄. Use of 60% H₂SO₄ increased the yield of 11. Decarboxylation of 10 affords 11. Sodium bicarbonate mediated self-condensation of methyl acetoacetate affords the methyl ester 12 of 10. Oxidation of the 4-methylcoumarins 6, 11 and 12 with SeO₂ gives the corresponding 4-formyl and 4-hydroxymethyl derivatives. The one-pot monosubstrated oligomerization of ethyl acetoacetate thus demonstrates a simple biomimetic type synthesis of a number of new dimethylcoumarin and trimethylcoumarin derivatives.

Self-condensation of ethyl acetoacetate (EAA) catalyzed by sodium bicarbonate was reported to yield dehydroacetic acid^{1,2} (1) and 2,7-dimethyl-4H-pyrano-[3,2-c]-2H-pyran-4,5-dione² (2a). It is known that acetone dicarboxylic acid, having active methylene and carbonyl components in the molecule, upon self-condensation³ afforded two coumarin derivatives; some polyketides cyclized⁴ to coumarins in the presence of sodium bicarbonate. By analogy, the formation of coumarin derivatives by self-condensation of ethyl acetoacetate was, therefore, anticipated. In fact, during the reinvestigation of the reaction, modification of the isolation procedure over that reported earlier^{1,2} led us to isolate several coumarins and to study the reaction products profile thoroughly for the first time without losing any information. The present study has provided a simple synthesis of some new highly substituted coumarin derivatives. The synthesis of these coumarins appears to be rather difficult following other routes.

Results and Discussion

The product mixture obtained upon refluxing ethyl acetoacetate in the presence of (catalytic amount of) sodium bicarbonate for 8 h with concomitant removal of alcohol by

distillation² was subjected to extensive chromatography over silica gel, and flash chromatography in some cases, instead of isolating by vacuum distillation^{1,2} and seven new crystalline compounds 3-9 were isolated in varying yields in addition to 1 and 2.

The ¹H nmr spectral data of dehydroacetic acid fit satisfactorily to the structure 1; but in chloroform solution, 1 remains preferably in a 4-pyrone form (1a), which has been indicated by the appearance in its ¹³C nmr spectrum of a peak at δ 180.9 assignable to a 4-pyrone carbonyl carbon.

The structure of the compound, m.p. 210°, assigned² previously as 2a, has now been revised as 4,7-dimethyl-2H-pyrano-[3,2-c]-2H-pyran-2,5-dione (2), primarily based on a 75 MHz ¹³C nmr spectral study (SFORD and APT): δ 20.16 (CH₃ at 4-C), 21.93 (CH₃ at 7-C), 99.16 (8-CH), 101.6 (4a-C), 112.45 (3-CH), 155.53 (4-C), 158.06 (7-C), 159.42 (8a-C), 165.42 (5-CO), 166.45 (2-CO). In the earlier reported² 20 MHz spectrum, a signal at δ 183.6 assigned to pyrone CO (2a) was a spurious one, and a singlet at δ 159.42 (7-C) of the least intensity was missing. The more deshielding of the oxygen bearing 7-C and attached methyl compared to 4-C and the attached methyl respectively, as well as 7-CH₃ protons (δ 2.30) are now obvious

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in the revised structure (2). Compound 2 on bromination with NBS afforded its 3-bromo derivative (2b) the structure of which was fully consistent with its spectral data. The X-ray crystallographic study on a single crystal of 2b confirmed the assigned structure, as evident from its ORTEP diagram (Fig. 1). Hence, the revised dilactone structure 2 for the parent compound, m.p. 212°, was unambiguously

Fig. 1. X-Ray diagram of compound 2.

settled. Incidentally, 2a, m.p. 183–84°, was reported⁵ to be formed by self-condensation of acetic anhydride in the presence of perchloric acid followed by treatment with water.

The ¹H and ¹³C spectra of 3–9 display remarkable similarity and thus the presence of a very similar system in them was suggested from the appearance of peaks assignable to two or three aromatic C–CH₃ groups, and one COOEt group in all of them save 4. The ir and uv spectral data and the positive colour reaction (yellow in 5% alcoholic KOH) pointed to their being coumarin derivatives. The presence of phenolic OH in 3, 4 and 7 was revealed from the forma-

Scheme 1. Reagents and condition: (i) H₂SO₄ (90%), 130°, 20 min, (ii) NaHCO₃, Δ, (iii) SeO₂, dioxan, Δ.

tion of their monoacetates **3a**, **4a** and **7a** respectively. Also the peaks at δ 13.26 and 11.45 in **3** and **7** respectively, were assigned to the chelated OH's. The placement of the OH group in **3** and **4** at 5-C rather than at 4-C was made on the basis of downfield shift of the proton H-8 to the extent of about 0.40 ppm in **3a** and **4a**. Similar deshielding of the proton *para* to OH in **7** was also observed in its acetate (**7a**). The alternative structure (**7'**) for **7**, though apparently compatible with the spectral data, was ruled out specially from the consideration of the chemical shifts of aromatic protons (6.80, 6.95 and 7.39). The expected downfield shift of H-3 by 0.16 ppm was observed in **4a**. The presence of COMe in **3** and **5** was revealed from their ^1H and ^{13}C nmr data and also from the deacetylation that they suffered on treatment with conc. H_2SO_4 to afford **4** and **6** respectively. Compound **3** produced **4** as the sole product, which is also obtainable from self-condensation of methyl acetoacetate. Similar deacetylation was also associated with hydrolysis

Scheme 2. Probable pathway of the formation of compound **3**.

and/or decarboxylation on conc. H_2SO_4 treatment. Thus, **5** yielded **10** and **11** along with **6**; on the other hand, **6** yielded **11**. On treatment with diazomethane **10** produced the corresponding methyl ester (**12**), which is identical with one self-condensation product of methyl acetoacetate. These conversions are reminiscent of the behaviour^{6,7} of mesitoic acid (\equiv 2,4,6-trimethylbenzoic acid) and its ester toward conc. H_2SO_4 and thus place unambiguously the two methyl groups *ortho* to the carboxy or carboethoxy group in **5** and **6**. The above transformations are outlined in Scheme 1.

Finally, the compound, m.p. 165° , obtained in very low yield (0.1%) was tentatively assigned the structure 3''-carboethoxy-7,9,10,10'-tetramethyltetrahydrofuran-[2,4-*de*]-4',10'-dihydro-5,6-naphthopyran-2,5-dione (**9**), mainly based on ^1H and ^{13}C nmr and spectral data, which revealed the presence of one methyl different from those in earlier compounds and its attachment to either an oxygenated carbon or an allylic carbon. The placement of the carboethoxy

group on an asymmetric saturated quaternary carbon, as shown, was based on the observation that CH_2 protons in CO_2Et being diastereotopic appeared as two sets of doublet of a quartet (split into 16 lines) in its ^1H nmr spectrum. The structure is merely a summation of spectral data and may not be the real one. Also its formation is not fully rationalisable from EAA and thus its unambiguous structural elucidation requires X-ray crystallographic study.

Therefore, all the above observations in conjunction with the ^1H , ^{13}C nmr and mass spectral data and mechanistic rationalisation led to the structures 3-acetyl-6-carboethoxy-5-hydroxy-4,7-dimethylcoumarin, m.p. 172° (**3**, yield 3%), 5-hydroxy-4,7-dimethylcoumarin, m.p. 254° (**4**, 1.4%), 3-acetyl-6-carboethoxy-4,5,7-trimethylcoumarin, m.p. 93° (**5**, 12%), 6-carboethoxy-4,5,7-trimethylcoumarin, m.p. 192° (**6**, 2.8%), 9-carboethoxy-10-hydroxy-2,4,8-trimethylbenzo-[3,4]-coumarin, m.p. 162° (**7**, 1.0%), 8-carboethoxy-3,7,9-trimethylfuran-[3,2-*c*]-coumarin, m.p. 150° (**8**, 2.0%) and 3''-carboethoxy-7,9,10,10'-tetramethyltetrahydrofuran-[2,4-*de*]-4',10'-dihydro-5,6-naphthopyran-2,5-dione, m.p. 165° (**9**, 0.1%) for the new products. Compounds **3**, **4**, **5**, **7** received additional support from their NOED studies. With diazomethane **10** formed its methyl ester (**12**) which was also obtained by the self-condensation of methyl acetoacetate.

Scheme 3. Probable pathway of the formation of compound **5**.

The presence of both electrophilic and nucleophilic sites as well as two non-discriminating electrophilic carbonyls in a simple ambident molecule initiates a combination of a number of competitive base-catalyzed intermolecular reactions, viz. C-acylation of the methylene carbanion and O-acylation of the enolate anion by attack on the ester carbonyl with concomitant loss of ethanol in each case, aldol-type condensation by attack of the methylene carbanion on the ketocarbonyl with loss of water, sometimes keeping one CO_2Et (*cf.* **3**, **5**, **6**, **7**) or COMe (*cf.* **3**, **5**) intact or finally

Scheme 4. Probable pathway of the formation of compound 7.

losing them (*cf.* 4, 6, 7). Thus, 1, 2, 3 (precursor of 4), 5 (precursor of 6) and 7, 8 and 9 were presumably formed from two, three, four, four, five, five and six EAA units respectively, as can be sorted out from the corresponding structures. The probable mechanisms for the formation of only 3, 5, 7 and 8 are delineated in Schemes 2, 3, 4 and 5 respectively, although the mechanistic rationale for the formation of the compounds 2, 2a, 4, 6, 7 and 7' have also been worked out similarly.

This one-pot monosubstrated reaction shows close analogy to the biogenetic path followed in plant cells for polyketide derived compounds⁶. And this reaction, though a long known one¹ was not studied earlier in respect of its reaction products profile to the advantage of a simple synthesis of highly substituted coumarins, the synthesis of which appears to be rather difficult by other routes. The synthetic value of this reaction lies in its cheap and readily available starting material and in simplicity of the procedure, though the yields range from moderate to low.

Ethyl acetoacetate upon refluxing with a little TFA or

Scheme 5. Probable pathway of the formation of compound 8.

upon refluxing alone afforded DAA (1) in 30 or 20% yield as the sole product along with unreacted EAA. However, EAA upon refluxing in presence of DMSO and catalytic amount of NaHCO_3 furnished 1 (6%), 2 (4%), 3 (3%) and 6 (2%).

Experimental

M.ps. measured in open capillary tubes are uncorrected. The uv spectra (aldehyde free ethanol) were measured on a Hitachi U-2000 spectrophotometer, and ir spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. The ^1H nmr (at 300 MHz) and ^{13}C nmr (at 75.5 MHz) spectra (CDCl_3) on a Bruker-300A spectrometer; the peak for TMS or solvent (CHCl_3 : δ 7.26 for ^1H and CDCl_3 : δ 77.0 for ^{13}C) was used as the internal standard and *J*-values are expressed in Hz. The products were unambiguously characterized by ir, uv, ^1H nmr, ^{13}C nmr and mass (at 70 eV) spectral analyses. Petrol refers to b.p. 60–80° fraction. The silica gel (60–120 mesh, Qualigens) was used for column chromatography; silica gel (230–400 mesh, SRL) was used for flash chromatography in an Eyela EFC-2000 instrument. The fractions were monitored using microscopic slides with silica gel G layer put on them by dipping in its chloroform slurry, taking out and drying in ambient temperature; similar fractions were combined.

Self-condensation of ethyl acetoacetate in presence of NaHCO_3 : Freshly distilled pure ethyl acetoacetate (100 g) was refluxed in presence of NaHCO_3 (60 mg) for 8 h under N_2 atmosphere and fractionated using a fractionating column. The low boiling fraction (b.p. 72–80°, 36 g, mostly ethanol) was collected as the distillate. The dark brown reaction mixture (70 g) when hot was dissolved in minimum amount of chloroform-ethyl acetate mixture and chromatographed over silica gel (2.4 kg), the elution being carried out with solvents and solvent mixtures of increasing polarity, viz. petrol [fractions 7–9], petrol-ethyl acetate (19 : 1) [fractions 10–16], petrol-ethyl acetate (9 : 1) [fractions 17–30], petrol-ethyl acetate (4 : 1) [fractions 31–45], petrol-ethyl acetate (3 : 2) [fractions 46–48], petrol-ethyl acetate (2 : 3) [fractions 49–52], petrol-ethyl acetate (1 : 4) [fractions 53–57] and ethyl acetate [fractions 58–60] in succession. The fractions were collected in 500 ml portions and monitored by running micro-tlc.

Dehydroacetic acid (1): The yellow solid residue (18 g) obtained from fractions 6–9 was rechromatographed over silica gel to yield a light yellow solid, which on crystallization from ethyl acetate-petrol (4 : 1) afforded colourless crystals of dehydroacetic acid (1; 10 g, 15%), m.p. 112°; ν_{max} 1735–1710 (CO), 1653, 1545, 1445, 1365, 1345, 1250, 1020, 990, 960, 915, 850, 770 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} (CDCl_3) 16.56

(1H, s, chelated OH), 5.84 (1H, s, H-5), 2.54 and 2.17 (each 3H, s, two CH₃'s); δ_C (CDCl₃) 168.99 (C-2), 99.71 (C-3), 180.97 (C-4), 101.22 (C-5), 160.91 (C-6), 204.96 (COCH₃), 29.63 and 20.43 (two CH₃'s).

4,7-Dimethyl-2H-pyrano-[3,2-c]-2H-pyran-2,5-dione (2): The yellow solid residue (15 g) from the fractions 17-22 was directly crystallized from chloroform-petrol to yield a cream coloured compound, which was further purified by flash chromatography followed by recrystallization from chloroform-petrol as colourless needles of **2** (8 g, 16%), m.p. 213°; ν_{\max} 1745, 1730, 1640, 1600, 1540, 1415, 1370, 1310, 1140, 1000, 990, 940, 850, 825, 775 cm⁻¹; δ_H (CDCl₃) 6.13 (1H, s, H-8), 6.01 (1H, s, H-3), 2.50, 2.29 (each 3H, s, 7-CH₃ and 4-CH₃); δ_C (CDCl₃) 166.45 (C-2), 99.16 (C-3), 153.53 (C-4), 101.60 (C-4a), 165.42 (C-5), 158.06 (C-7), 112.45 (C-8), 159.4 (C-8a), 21.93 (4-CH₃), 20.16 (7-CH₃), 159.42 (C-8a).

3-Acetyl-6-carboethoxy-5-hydroxy-4,7-dimethylcoumarin (3): The residue (7.2 g) from the fractions 12-14 was directly subjected to repeated crystallizations from ethyl acetate-petrol to furnish colourless needles of **3** (1.9 g, 3%), m.p. 172°; ν_{\max} 1710, 1700, 1655, 1615, 1590, 1400, 1380, 1315, 1255, 1185, 1125, 1095, 955, 810 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} (log ϵ) 312 (3.99), 258 (4.27), 209 nm (4.28); λ_{\max} (EtOH + OH⁻) 292 (4.05), 218 (4.36) nm; δ_H (CDCl₃) 13.26 (1H, s, chelated 5-ArOH), 6.60 (1H, s, H-8), 4.43 (2H, q, *J* 7.2, Ar-COOCH₂CH₃), 2.56 (6H, s, two Ar-CH₃'s), 2.49 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 1.42 (3H, t, *J* 7.2, Ar-COOCH₂CH₃); δ_C (CDCl₃) 157.88 (C-2), 108.36 (C-3), 156.58 (C-4), 107.64 (C-4a), 164.64 (C-5), 126.15 (C-6), 146.36 (C-7), 111.42 (C-8), 151.92 (C-8a), 200.74 (Ar-COCH₃), 171.88 (Ar-COOCH₂CH₃), 62.29 (Ar-COOCH₂CH₃), 31.12, 24.61, 20.16 (three CH₃'s), 14.01 (Ar-COOCH₂CH₃); *m/z* (% rel. int.) 305 (M⁺+1, 5), 304 (M⁺, C₁₆H₁₆O₆, 15), 258 (M⁺-EtOH, 11), 243 (M⁺-EtOH-Me, 12.5), 231 (M⁺-CO₂Et, 11.5), 230 (M⁺-EtOH-CO, 100), 215 (6), 202 (5), 188 (M⁺-CO₂Et-COCH₃, 18.2), 160 (10).

5-Hydroxy-4,7-dimethylcoumarin (4): The gummy residue (6 g) from the fractions 39-42 (insoluble in chloroform) was dissolved in minimum volume of acetone and rechromatographed over silica gel to furnish **4** crystallizing from acetone-petrol as yellow needles, (0.52 g; 1.4%), m.p. 254-56°; ν_{\max} 3460-3395, 3050, 1655, 1612, 1510, 1420, 1400, 1380, 1340, 1300, 1250, 1100, 1075, 920, 850, 830 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} (log ϵ) 303 (4.09), 254 (3.92), 212 nm (4.34); λ_{\max} (EtOH + OH⁻) 392 (3.83), 313 (3.92), 275 (4.07) 251 (3.98), 222 nm (4.19); δ_H (d₆-acetone) 6.63 (1H, s, H-6), 6.60 (1H, s, H-8), 5.96 (1H, s, H-3), 2.57 (3H, s, 4-CH₃), 2.28 (3H, s, 7-CH₃); δ_C (d₆-DMSO) 160.11 (C-2), 112.19, 112.08 (C-6 and C-3), 155.07, 154.85 (C-4 and

C-8a), 156.66 (C-5), 106.60 (C-4a), 107.96 (C-8), 23.63 (4-CH₃), 21.33 (7-CH₃); *m/z* (% rel. int.) 191 (M⁺+1, 16.5), 190 (M⁺, 100), 163 (10.7), 162 (M⁺-CO, 93.3), 161 (M⁺-CO-H⁺, 50.6), 147 (M⁺-CO-Me⁺, 8.7), 145 (5.6), 133 (5.1), 91 (11.5).

3-Acetyl-6-carboethoxy-4,5,7-trimethylcoumarin (5): The yellow mother liquor obtained during first crystallization of **2** on keeping at room temperature for 48 h, furnished heavy crystals which were purified through repeated crystallizations from methanol to furnish **5** as colourless heavy needles (5 g, 12%), m.p. 93°; ν_{\max} 1725, 1710, 1600, 1545, 1425, 1390, 1345, 1285, 1270, 1230, 1180, 1090, 1020, 950, 860, 775 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} (log ϵ) 296 (4.07), 277 (3.96), 210 nm (4.39); δ_H (CDCl₃) 6.91 (1H, s, H-8), 4.36 (2H, q, *J* 7.2, COOCH₂CH₃), 2.51 (3H, s, COCH₃), 2.47, 2.43, 2.26 (each 3H, s, three CH₃'s), 1.33 (3H, t, *J* 7.2, COOCH₂CH₃); δ_C (CDCl₃) 157.6 (C-2), 117.0 (C-3), 153.4 (C-4), 117.0 (C-4a), 134.0 (C-5), 128.4 (C-6), 139.0 (C-7), 116.5 (C-8), 150.5 (C-8a), 201.0 (Ar-COCH₃), 168.8 (Ar-COOCH₂CH₃), 61.3 (Ar-COOCH₂CH₃), 30.8 (Ar-COCH₃), 21.2, 20.7, 19.4 (three CH₃'s), 13.92 (Ar-COOCH₂CH₃); *m/z* (% rel. int.) 303 (M⁺+1, 19.2), 302 (M⁺, 88.2), 288 (7.6), 287 (M⁺-Me⁺, 43.1), 274 (M⁺-CO, 18.9), 273 (M⁺-Et⁺, 100.0), 260 (9.4), 259 (M⁺-CO-Me⁺, 24.6), 258 (M⁺-Et⁺-Me⁺, 10.9), 257 (M⁺-OEt⁺, 58.5), 256 (10.0), 255 (97.9).

6-Carboethoxy-4,5,7-trimethylcoumarin (6): The gummy solid residue (4.4 g) obtained from the fractions 34-36 on rechromatography over silica gel furnished a solid which was purified through repeated crystallizations from acetone-petrol to furnish **6** as grey needles (1.6 g, 2.8%), m.p. 192°; ν_{\max} 1735, 1715, 1605, 1425, 1270, 1180, 1100, 1072, 1035, 920, 865 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} (log ϵ) 285 (4.11), 210 nm (4.45); δ_H (CDCl₃) 6.96 (1H, s, H-8), 6.14 (1H, s, H-3), 4.36 (2H, q, *J* 6.9, 6-COOCH₂CH₃), 2.54, 2.28 (each 3H, s, two CH₃'s), 1.35 (3H, t, *J* 6.9, 6-COOCH₂CH₃); δ_C (CDCl₃) 159.71 (C-2), 116.64 (C-3), 154.65 (C-4), 117.16 (C-4a), 133.44 (C-5), 133.12 (C-6), 138.29 (C-7), 116.94 (C-8), 153.5 (C-8a), 169.21 (6-COOCH₂CH₃), 61.3 (6-COOCH₂CH₃), 25.37, 20.35, 19.46 (three CH₃'s), 14.0 (6-COOCH₂CH₃); *m/z* (% rel. int.) 261 (M⁺+1, 15.73), 260 (M⁺, 89.32), 232 (24.6), 231 (M⁺-Et⁺, 20.4), 216 (15.7), 215 (100), 214 (M⁺-EtOH, 24.0), 204 (M⁺-C₂H₄-CO, 16.3), 203 (M⁺-Et⁺-CO, 20.7), 187 (24.6), 186 (48.9), 185 (5.9), 160 (11.5), 159 (52.5), 158 (19.5).

9-Carboethoxy-10-hydroxy-2,4,8-trimethylbenzo-[3,4]-coumarin (7): The residue (2 g) from the fractions 26-28 upon rechromatography yielded a white mass, crystallizing from chloroform-petrol to furnish **7** as white needles (0.5 g, 1%), m.p. 162°; ν_{\max} 1710, 1675, 1600, 1445, 1365,

1280, 1220, 1185, 1140, 1100, 1055, 850, 800, 755 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} (log ϵ) 349 (3.94), 337 (3.96), 280 (3.87), 244 (4.56), 216 nm (4.37); λ_{max} (EtOH + OH^-) 379 (3.47), 302 (4.04), 229 nm (4.34); δ_{H} (CDCl_3) 11.45 (1H, s, chelated Ar-OH), 7.39 (1H, s, H-7), 6.95 (1H, s, ArH), 6.80 (1H, s, ArH), 4.41 (2H, q, J 7.2, Ar- $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 2.63, 2.40, 2.30 (each 3H, s, three CH_3 's), 1.39 (3H, t, J 7.2, Ar- $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$); δ_{C} (CDCl_3) 116.72 (C-1), 132.99 (C-2), 116.52 (C-3), 134.06 (C-4), 103.96 (C-4a), 162.37 (C-5), 148.00 (C-6a), 118.17 (C-7), 136.43 (C-8), 135.22 (C-9), 164.75 (C-10), 115.65 (C-10a), 151.02 (C-10b), 169.22 (Ar- $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 61.22 (Ar- $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 22.65, 21.64, 19.27 (three CH_3 's), 14.03 (Ar- $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$); m/z (% rel. int.) 327 ($\text{M}^+ + 1$, 20), 326 (M^+ , $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_5$, 100), 298 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{C}_2\text{H}_4$, 9.7), 297 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{Et}^+$, 25.1), 282 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{CH}_3\text{CHO}$, 17.6), 281 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{OEt}$, 97.7), 280 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{EtOH}$, 33), 254 (9), 253 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{COOEt}$, 24), 252 (52.5), 225 (14.5), 182 (13), 181 (16), 165 (13), 153 (12), 152 (17.3).

8-Carboethoxy-3,7,9-trimethylfurano[3,2-*c*]coumarin (8): The dark gummy solid residue (4 g) from fractions 31-32 was subjected to flash chromatography to furnish **8**, crystallizing from acetone-petrol as shining heavy needles (2 g, 2%), m.p. 150°; ν_{max} 1740, 1710, 1615, 1598, 1560, 1430, 1370, 1310, 1260, 1240, 1210, 1170, 1155, 1100, 1050, 1020, 960, 920, 880, 765 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} (log ϵ) 250 (4.02), 222 nm (4.53); δ_{H} (CDCl_3) 7.71 (1H, s, H-2), 6.97 (1H, s, H-6), 4.40 (2H, q, J 7.1, Ar- $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 2.73, 2.38, 2.32 (each 3H, s, three CH_3 's), 1.38 (3H, t, J 7.1 Ar- $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$); δ_{C} (CDCl_3) 134.90 (C-2), 119.69 (C-3), 112.02 (C-3a), 159.98 (C-4), 151.57 (C-5a), 116.35 (C-6), 135.66 (C-7), 131.22 (C-8), 132.57 (C-9), 107.00 (C-9a), 157.66 (C-9b), 61.09 (8- $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 19.43, 19.01, 14.03 (three CH_3 's), 13.19 (8- $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$); m/z (% rel. int.) 301 ($\text{M}^+ + 1$, 15.2), 300 (M^+ , $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_5$, 78.4), 272 (8.9), 271 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{Et}^+$, 31.7), 257 (7.0), 256 (16.0), 255 ($\text{M}^+ - \text{OEt}$, 100), 254 (48.8), 229 (9.1), 228 (7.6), 227 (11.6), 226 (17), 129 (9.1), 128 (27.4), 127 (11.6), 115 (12.1).

Compound 9: The mother liquor obtained during crystallization of **3** and showing a second minor spot (close R_f) in addition to the spot of **3** was evaporated under reduced pressure. The residue was subjected to flash chromatography using petrol-ethylacetate (19 : 1) as the eluent to afford compound **9**, crystallizing from chloroform-petrol mixture as colourless crystals (50 mg, 0.1%), m.p. 165°; ν_{max} 1705, 1642, 1585, 1540, 1475, 1445, 1395, 1375, 1360, 1335, 1280, 1260, 1218, 1185, 1110, 1065, 1040, 1000, 885, 830, 740 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} (CDCl_3) 8.08 (1H, s), 6.79 (1H, s), 5.88 (1H, s), 4.32 (2H, m, Ar- $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 2.36, 2.27, 2.25, 1.73 (each 3H, s, four CH_3 's), 1.37 (3H, t, J 7, Ar- $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$); δ_{C} (CDCl_3) 165.80, 164.92, 162.60,

161.36, 157.51, 146.49, 139.66, 125.30, 112.08, 99.39 and 73.83 (eleven-C -'s), 120.44, 114.97, 100.89 (three CH 's), 60.52 (CH_2), 26.91, 21.55, 19.99, 19.06, 14.24 (five CH_3 's); m/z (% rel. int.) 368 (M^+ , 14), 355 (4.9), 354 (29.8), 353 (100), 351 (6.1), 326 (6.4), 325 (30.5), 323 (7.3), 307 (8.8), 305 (7.2).

Acetylation of compounds 3, 4 and 7: Each of the compounds **3**, **4** and **7** was separately treated with acetic anhydride (1 ml) and pyridine (1 ml) for 24 h at room temperature. The reaction mixture was then poured into crushed ice, neutralized with 2N HCl and extracted with chloroform. The chloroform extract was washed with water and dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . On removal of excess solvent a solid mass was obtained, which was purified through column chromatography and subsequent crystallization from chloroform-petrol. 20 mg of **3** yielded its 5-acetyl derivative (**3a**) as cream coloured crystals (18 mg), m.p. 148–150°; ν_{max} 1775, 1725, 1710, 1615, 1550, 1440, 1375, 1350, 1275, 1240, 1185, 1090, 1060, 1010, 955, 860 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} (CDCl_3) 7.06 (1H, s, H-8), 4.32 (2H, q, J 7, Ar- $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 2.46 (3H, s, Ar- COCH_3), 2.40, 2.34 (each 3H, s, 4- and 7- CH_3 's), 2.25 (3H, s, Ar- OCOCH_3), 1.32 (3H, t, J 7, Ar- $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$); δ_{C} (CDCl_3) 157.33 (C-2), 141.99 (C-3), 153.82 (C-4), 112.17 (C-4a), 146.93 (C-5), 128.91 (C-6), 125.05 (C-7), 116.90 (C-8), 147.59 (C-8a), 200.14 (Ar- COCH_3), 168.71 (Ar- $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$)*, 165.31 (Ar- OCOCH_3)*, 61.76 (Ar- $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 31.01, 20.94, 20.48, 18.17 (four CH_3 's), 14.06 (Ar- $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$) (*assignment interchangeable). Compound **4** (20 mg) gave the monoacetate (**4a**) as fine white needles (95%), m.p. 200–202°; ν_{max} 1770, 1735, 1625, 1490, 1450, 1380, 1365, 1220, 1200, 1150, 1075, 1035, 1015, 900, 880 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} (CDCl_3) 7.01 (1H, s, H-6), 6.74 (1H, s, H-8), 6.12 (1H, s, H-3), 2.43, 2.38, 2.32 (each 3H, s, three CH_3 's); δ_{C} (CDCl_3) 159.9 (C-2), 115.8 (C-3), 154.6 (C-4), 111.4 (C-4a), 147.3 (C-5), 120.2 (C-6), 142.5 (C-7), 115.5 (C-8), 150.8 (C-8a), 168.9 (5- OCOCH_3), 22.5 ($-\text{OCOCH}_3$), 21.3 (two CH_3 's). Compound **7** (30 mg) furnished the monoacetate **7a** (25 mg) as colourless needles, m.p. 143–145°; ν_{max} 1760, 1735, 1720, 1445, 1360, 1300, 1250, 1200, 1180, 1122, 1085, 1030, 1015, 900, 880, 855 cm^{-1} ; δ_{H} (CDCl_3) 7.84 (1H, s, H-7), 7.02 (1H, s, ArH), 7.01 (1H, s, ArH), 4.41 (2H, q, J 7.1, Ar- $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$), 2.69, 2.49, 2.40, 2.33 (each 3H, s, four CH_3 's), 1.39 (3H, t, J 7.1, Ar- $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$); δ_{C} (CDCl_3) 123.75 (C-1), 132.56 (C-2), 116.41 (C-3), 133.53 (C-4), 112.62 (C-4a), 157.10 (C-5), 151.73 (C-6a), 124.83 (C-7), 136.95 (C-8), 137.27 (C-9), 145.81 (C-10), 115.47 (C-10a), 152.17 (C-10b), 169.53 (Ar- OCOCH_3)*, 169.23 (Ar- $\text{COOCH}_2\text{CH}_3$)*, 61.1 (Ar-

COOCH₂CH₃), 22.1, 21.4, 20.9, 19.4 (four CH₃'s), 14.0 (Ar-COOCH₂CH₃) (*assignments interchangeable).

Bromination of 2 with NBS : Compound **2** (100 mg) was refluxed with NBS (50 mg) in chloroform-ethanol mixture on a water-bath for 30 min. The reaction mixture was then filtered and the filtrate was concentrated. The solid residue was purified by column chromatography followed by crystallization from chloroform-petrol to the monobromo derivative **2b** as colourless needles (60%), m.p. 185°; ν_{\max} 1735, 1640, 1575, 1510, 1360, 1290, 1060, 1000, 925, 830, 770 cm⁻¹; δ_{H} (CDCl₃) 6.18 (1H, s, H-8), 2.77 (3H, s, 7-CH₃), 2.34 (3H, s, 4-CH₃).

X-Ray crystallographic study of the monobromo derivative 2b : The colourless prisms were grown from a mixture of n-propanal and acetone and a crystal of dimensions 0.25 × 0.30 × 0.10 mm was selected for X-ray analysis. The ORTEP diagram of **2b** (Fig. 1), derived from the X-ray crystallographic analyses was received through the kind courtesy of Professor Z. Dauter (York University, U.K.) and Dr. Sabita Das (York University, on leave from Victoria Institution, Calcutta). The list of refined coordinates and some other relevant data are as follows : C₁₀H₇O₄Br; μ_{r} = 1084.08, monoclinic, space group P2₁/C; a = 10.87 Å, b = 11.45 Å, c = 8.05 Å, β = 105.3°, V = 966.40 Å³, Z = 4, D_{m} = 1.86 g cm⁻³, D_{c} = 1.86 g cm⁻³, $\lambda_{\text{c}} k_{\alpha}$ = 1.54182 Å, R = 0.066 for observed reflections.

Treatment of 5 and 12 with concentrated H₂SO₄ : Compound **5** (0.2 g) was dissolved in 85–90% H₂SO₄ (2 ml) and heated on an oil-bath at 130° with constant stirring for 20 min. The mixture was then poured on crushed ice (5 g) and the precipitated solid was washed successively with water, aqueous NaHCO₃ and again with water, and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. The solid was then chromatographed over silica gel. On chromatography, **4** was isolated from petrol-ethyl acetate (9 : 1) eluates; while **10** was isolated from the polar fractions of petrol-ethyl acetate (7 : 3) eluates. It was found insoluble in chloroform, and was crystallized from acetone-petrol, (40%), m.p. 224° and identified as 6-carboxy-4,5,7-trimethylcoumarin (**10**); ν_{\max} 3400 (br, COOH), 1700, 1600, 1540, 1425, 1380, 1280, 1180, 1070, 1025, 840 cm⁻¹; δ_{H} (d₆-acetone) 7.05 (1H, s, H-8), 6.21 (1H, s, H-3), 2.67, 2.65, 2.36 (each 3H, s, three CH₃'s); δ_{C} (d₆-acetone) 159.52 (C-2), 117.08 (C-3), 155.28 (C-4), 117.84 (C-4a), 135.01 (C-5), 133.81 (C-6), 138.44 (C-7), 116.92 (C-8), 154.81 (C-8a), 170.32 (Ar-COOH), 25.12, 20.36, 19.41 (three CH₃'s). The colourless compound obtained from the earlier fractions of petrol-ethyl acetate (19 : 1) eluates was crystallized from chloroform-petrol and was characterized as 4,5,7-trimethylcoumarin (**11**; 40%), m.p. 180°; ν_{\max} 1710, 1615, 1600, 1550, 1485, 1455, 1440,

1380, 1360, 1245, 1230, 1200, 1160, 1065, 1035, 990, 895, 870, 850 cm⁻¹; δ_{H} (CDCl₃) 7.0 (1H, bs), 6.88 (1H, bs), 6.15 (1H, bs), 2.67 (3H, s), 2.59 (3H, s), 2.36 (3H, s).

Similar treatment of **12** (20 mg) with conc. H₂SO₄ was done following the same procedure, when **11** (8 mg), m.p. 180° was obtained as the sole product.

Conversion of 3 to 4 : In a similar way when **3** (30 mg) was treated with H₂SO₄ (80%, 1 ml) for 20 min at 130° and worked up as usual, **4** was formed as the sole product (20 mg), m.p. 254°.

Methylation of 10 with diazomethane : To compound **10** (50 mg) taken in diethyl ether-methanol (25 ml), excess of diazomethane was added at 0–5° and then the reaction mixture was left overnight at room temperature. On removal of the excess of solvent under reduced pressure the methyl ester (**12**) was obtained, crystallizing from chloroform-petrol as white needles (45 mg), m.p. 164°; ν_{\max} 1735, 1720, 1600, 1430, 1420, 1350, 1270, 1250, 1190, 1175, 1100, 1070, 1030, 950, 905, 890, 860, 825 cm⁻¹; δ_{H} (CDCl₃) 7.01 (1H, s, H-8), 6.18 (1H, s, H-3), 3.92 (3H, s, Ar-COOCH₃), 2.58, 2.56, 2.30 (each 3H, s, three CH₃'s); δ_{C} (CDCl₃) 159.90 (C-2), 116.74 (C-3), 117.08 (C-8), 117.28 (C-4a), 154.83 (C-4), 133.39 and 133.33 (C-5 and C-7), 138.52 (C-6), 153.67 (C-8a), 169.90 (Ar-COOCH₃), 52.41 (Ar-COOCH₃), 25.54, 20.63, 19.67 (three CH₃'s).

SeO₂ oxidation of 6, 11 and 12 : Compound **6** (50 mg) was refluxed with sublimed SeO₂ (100 mg) in dry dioxane (3ml) for 20 h. Dioxane was then removed from the product mixture under reduced pressure and the residue was subjected to chromatography. From the less polar fractions [petrol-ethyl acetate (9 : 1)] the solid obtained was crystallized from chloroform-petrol, (35%), m.p. 172°, which was later identified as **15** from its spectral data; ν_{\max} 1740, 1715, 1605, 1430, 1360, 1350, 1310, 1275, 1240, 1185, 1110, 1070, 1050, 1030, 920, 880, 860, 845 cm⁻¹; δ_{H} (CDCl₃) 10.40 (1H, s, 4-CHO), 7.03 (1H, s, H-8), 6.20 (1H, s, H-3), 4.42 (2H, q, *J* 7, Ar-COOCH₂CH₃), 2.61, 2.34 (each 3H, s, two CH₃'s), 1.40 (3H, t, *J* 7, Ar-COOCH₂CH₃). The more polar fractions [petrol-ethyl acetate (7 : 3)] yielded compound **16** (30%), crystallizing from chloroform-petrol, m.p. 155°; ν_{\max} 3360 (OH), 1720, 1695, 1605, 1545, 1435, 1385, 1365, 1300, 1210, 1195, 1180, 1100, 1090, 1050, 1000, 935, 860 cm⁻¹.

Similar oxidation of **11** with SeO₂ following the same procedure yielded two compounds, separated by chromatography over silica gel. From the less polar fractions [petrol-ethyl acetate (9 : 1)] **13** was obtained, crystallizing from chloroform-petrol, (40%), m.p. 166°; ν_{\max} 1720, 1696, 1615, 1595, 1540, 1485, 1450, 1380, 1345, 1290, 1220, 1185, 1150, 1075, 1025, 890, 848, 720 cm⁻¹; δ_{H} (CDCl₃)

10.48 (1H, s, 4-CHO), 7.04 (1H, s, H-6), 6.97 (1H, s, H-8), 6.46 (1H, s, H-3), 2.51, 2.40 (each 3H, s, two CH₃'s); δ_C (CDCl₃) 159.77 (C-2), 129.04 (C-3), 155.43 (C-4), 112.75 (C-4a), 135.16 (C-5), 116.06 and 115.86 (C-6 and C-8), 143.65 (C-7), 150.50 (C-8a), 190.98 (4-CHO), 23.62, 21.40 (two CH₃'s). The more polar fractions of petrol-ethyl acetate (7 : 3) eluate of the above chromatogram afforded **14**, which was crystallized from chloroform-methanol, (30%), m.p. 191°; ν_{\max} 3380 (OH), 1710, 1690, 1615, 1600, 1450, 1310, 1220, 1150, 1080, 915, 850 cm⁻¹; δ_H (d₆-DMSO) 7.0 (1H, s, H-6), 6.92 (1H, s, H-8), 6.46 (1H, s, H-3), 4.78 (2H, s, CH₂OH), 2.52, 2.27 (each 3H, s, two CH₃'s); δ_C (d₆-DMSO) 160.01 (C-2), 110.35 (C-3), 158.94 (C-4), 114.96 (C-4a), 136.49 (C-5), 129.38 (C-6), 141.71 (C-7), 115.38 (C-8), 154.68 (C-8a), 61.76 (4-CH₂OH), 23.19, 20.66 (two CH₃'s).

SeO₂ oxidation of **12** was accomplished following the same procedure. **17**, the aldehyde derivative was isolated from the less polar fractions [petrol-ethyl acetate (9 : 1)], (40%), m.p. 183°; ν_{\max} 1720, 1700, 1600, 1550, 1430, 1275, 1175, 1050, 950, 875 cm⁻¹. The alcohol derivative **18** was isolated from the more polar fractions [petrol-ethyl acetate (7 : 3)], (20%), m.p. 185°; ν_{\max} 3360 (OH), 1725, 1695, 1600, 1430, 1265, 1190, 1170, 1090, 1050, 950, 850 cm⁻¹.

Self-condensation of ethyl acetoacetate under different other conditions : Ethyl acetoacetate upon refluxing alone in a similar fashion as described earlier, yielded dehydroacetic acid (**1**) as the only product. (20%) with unreacted ethyl acetoacetate. Ethyl acetoacetate upon refluxing with a little trifluoroacetic acid afforded dehydroacetic acid as the sole product (30%) along with unreacted ethyl acetoacetate. However, ethyl acetoacetate (70 ml) upon refluxing in presence of DMSO (1 ml) and NaHCO₃ (50 mg)

under similar experimental condition, furnished **1** (6%), **2** (4%), **3** (3%) and **6** (2%).

Self-condensation of methyl acetoacetate : Methyl acetoacetate was refluxed with NaHCO₃ under same conditions as those in the case of ethyl acetoacetate. **1** (8%), **4** and **12** (<2% each) were obtained along with another compound, m.p. 146°, which could not be characterized.

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